

insertion of insect stylets into the feeding sites and indicate that mechanical barriers were not involved in varietal resistance.

Host range studies involving 56 plant species indicated that *N. virescens* can survive and breed only on rice, while *N. nigropictus* has a host range that includes rice, sugarcane, and five graminaceous weeds. *N. nigropictus* showed greater preference for *Leersia hexandra* than for any other plant including TN1 rice. However, both species could lay eggs even on nonhosts. *N. virescens* made more feeding marks and excreted less honeydew when caged on the host plants suited to *N. nigropictus*, suggest-

ing that narrow host specificity may be due to an imbalance in phagostimulants or the presence of phagodeterrents.

These results show that chemosensory, particularly gustatory, stimuli play an important role in host selection in green leafhoppers.

The biochemical causes of resistance to leafhoppers in rice were also investigated. The total phenol content of resistant varieties was relatively higher than that of the susceptible TN1, but it was also high in *L. hexandra*. Thus, individual phenolic compounds may play a role in susceptibility or resistance.

The role of amino acids was not clear because their concentration was low

both in resistant rice varieties and in *L. hexandra*, which was the most suitable host for *N. nigropictus*.

Feeding stimulation and inhibition by various chemicals and plant extracts of resistant and susceptible varieties were bioassayed. Sucrose was highly stimulatory and a few amino acids slightly stimulated feeding. Amino acid derivatives, organic acids, and phenolic compounds were strongly deterrent. Similarly, both GLH species had low preference for chloroform and acetone extracts of resistant varieties, but similar extracts from susceptible plants were readily accepted. ■

Varietal resistance of rice to leaf folder

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A trial was conducted through the upland rice varietal screening program to select varieties suitable for dryland paddy cultivation in the hilly zone of Karnataka in 1980 kharif. Twenty-one entries were included in this trial, replicated three times. During the trial, incidence of the leaf folder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* was severe, but some varieties were observed to have lower levels of damage. The damage on different varieties was recorded (see table). ARC25, KMP133, and KMP58 had minimum damage and were also moderately resistant to blast. ■

Extent of damage^a by leaf folder in different rice varieties. Karnataka, India.

Entry	Leaf damage (%)
Kala keni	69.4
CR222-MW-10	65.5
ARC25	10.6
Black Gora	69.0
Bala	100.0
IR6115-1-1-1	100.0
OR165-85-12	66.9
KMP39	47.2
KMP(A) 57	75.0
OR165-28-14B	51.2
OR165-18-8	100.0
CRM13-3241	100.0
N22	42.4
MR262	75.0
CR143-2-2	100.0
CR245-1	100.0
KMP58	28.7
IET1444	96.7
KMP133	11.8
KMP134	39.4
Jaya	71.8

^aAv of 3 replications.

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GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Drought resistance

Selection pathways for dryland rice breeding

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Progenies of two rice crosses — IR3135 (IR1539-823-1-4/IR1917-3-17) and

IR3189 (IR1721-11-13-20-1-2/C4-63) — were grown and selected under wetland and dryland conditions. The result was three different selection pathways. The pathways (F₂ and F₃) were: 1 = dryland/dryland; 2 = wetland/dryland; and 3 = wetland/wetland lines. F₄ from the two crosses and three pathways were compared under dryland conditions for grain yield and yield components.

The pathways affected neither the grain yield nor the yield components. The two crosses differed significantly in 100-grain weight, tiller number, and plant height, but did not differ significantly in grain yield, panicle number, or panicle length. The variables studied showed no significant interactions.

Statistically nonsignificant mean squares and relatively small variance

components were observed for pathways and crosses \times pathways interactions, suggesting that environment had a minimal effect on the comparative yielding ability of the two crosses.

Because only two crosses were studied, these results are not conclusive. But it appears probable that there are no advantages in early generation selection under dryland conditions. Consid-

ering the many operational advantages, dryland rice breeders should consider growing all early generation materials under wetland conditions. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Adverse soils tolerance

Identification of iron toxicity in Brazil

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Symptoms similar to those of iron toxicity have been observed in rice-producing regions of Santa Catarina State, Brazil. In 1977, their cause was studied for the first time.

Many brownish spots appeared on the tips of older leaves of affected plants

and later spread to the basal parts. The leaves (except the midrib) turned brown and dried. In many areas the brown color turned reddish. The roots were dark brown and were damaged. All the symptoms were observed at the maximum tillering stage.

At the panicle initiation stage and at maturity, samples of roots, culms, and leaves were collected from a rice farmer's field at Camboriú, Itajaí River Valley. Simultaneously plant samples were collected from another plot where

no symptoms were observed. The samples were sent to different laboratories for analysis of the contents of nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, iron, and manganese. One laboratory replicated the sample analysis twice.

The results were compared with those found for various elements by Tanaka and Yoshida in 1970. The iron content of the affected leaves at maturity averaged 846 ppm. Iron toxicity was confirmed as the cause of the symptoms. ■

A mass-screening method for salt tolerance of rice varieties at seedling stage

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Rice varieties at the seedling stage were screened for salt tolerance in the greenhouse at RRS in Chinsurah.

The experiment was designed to investigate the effects of salinity on seedling growth (up to 21 days) of 100 rice varieties — including the standard variety SR26 B — under 17.5 mmho/cm of saline water (see figure). The salt solution was prepared by adding sodium chloride to distilled water. Normal and saline water were maintained at a suitable level in sterilized cylindrical, glass jars (9.5 cm \times 5.0 cm). Salt solution was estimated by determining electrical conductivity in mmho/cm at 25° C of the solution.

Blotting paper rolls were inserted in the glass jars. Two sets of jars, one for each treatment (normal and saline water), were placed side by side. Five seeds of each variety were made to adhere to the blotting paper by means of their seed hairs so the embryos

Germination and seedling growth of the same variety in saline water (left) and fresh water (right).

remained submerged.

Each variety was allowed to germinate in the culture jars. Water, i.e. fresh and saline, was added to the jars and maintained to a depth of 7.0 cm. The salt solution was adjusted to the desired

concentration at weekly intervals. The salt tolerance of each variety at seedling stage was determined by length, fresh weight, dry weight, and water content of root and shoot.

A high concentration of saline water delayed germination and depressed seedling growth for all varieties. General effects of salinity were darkening of the green color, withering of leaf tips, followed by yellowing and drying. A high degree of salinity significantly reduced the length of the root and shoot of the rice seedlings. Root growth was more depressed than was shoot growth.

Marked varietal differences in salt tolerance were observed (see table). Hamilton (selected from Nonabokra), a newly recommended variety, showed the best root growth. Root length development in BPI 76 was poor. Hamilton and Dholabokra had significantly higher values for shoot length than the other varieties. The adverse effect of salinity on shoot length was most pronounced in BPI 76.

Fresh weight and dry matter production of root and shoot also were depressed by salinity. Hamilton gave higher values for fresh weight and water content of root and shoot. But Dheral and Marichsail proved better in shoot